

JOURNAL ON COMMUNICATIONS

ISSN:1000-436X

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Study of Seasonal Climatology and Interannual Variability of Ionosphere over Thar Desert, India

Gopal Mondal*

Departments of Mathematics, Vivekananda Mission Mahavidyalaya, West Bengal, 721645, India

ABSTRACT: The behaviour of Ionosphere over desert region in long-term scale, however, has not been well recognized by the Ionosphere research community. This study demonstrates the significant climatological variation of the ionosphere over the great Thar desert for the first time, using five years of ionospheric data for the period 2020-2024, retrieved from the COSMIC-RO satellite. In addition to demonstrating insightful information on long-term electron concentration (Ne) in the Ionospheric E layer, this study primarily focuses on long-term variability of important ionospheric parameters such as NmF2, HmF2, and IECs. Both, NmF2 and IECs exhibit semi-annual variation with twin-peaks during the summer and spring season, whereas HmF2 shows annual variation with an annual peak during post-summer and an annual dip during the winter. The findings decisively demonstrate the significance of integrating multiple ionospheric parameters in studying a desert region where not a single long term ionospheric study conducted before using LEO satellite information. This research sets a strong foundation as background knowledge for future investigations in quantifying disturbance levels and the potential for communication interruptions in satellite broadcasting, improving navigational services during various geophysical phenomena.

Keywords: Desert-Ionosphere, Thar-desert, E-layer, ECR, LSA, HSA, COSMIC-RO

1. Introduction:

Geographical features, topography, and differential land-use patterns on the Indian subcontinent are complex. The Arabian Sea, Bay of Bengal, and the Indian Ocean surrounded the western, eastern, and southern parts of the subcontinent respectively and the Himalaya is situated in the northern part extending up to northeast India in the east. All of these combine to play a major role in deciding the lower atmospheric climate of the Indian region and its subregions.

In the Indian low-latitude region, the great Thar Desert exhibits unique lower atmospheric phenomena generated due to extreme thermal variability, spread around 19.61 million ha in the western part of India, which plays a sensitive role in the atmospheric circulation. In the summer season extremely hot wind of temperature 40-50°C, locally called “Loo,” blows, established as one of the key climatic features in this region. Also, the most common event, sudden and violent dust storms during the pre-monsoon season in this area [1], has a huge impact on the socio-economic structure of human habitats here. It should be mentioned here that most of the deserts, with their extreme thermal variability and atmospheric vulnerability, located in low- to mid-latitude regions, and spread over a vast region, play a crucial role in the Hadley circulation of global atmospheric circulation [2-6]. In this low-latitude region, Hadley circulation has an important role in the stability of the height of the tropopause as well as climate change forces, such as sea surface temperature (SST) changes [7] (e.g., El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO)) and stratospheric ozone depletion [8-9], etc. Now the question is whether the ionosphere over the desert region shows similar long-term variability like that of the equatorial and low-latitude regions.

The ionosphere over the equatorial and low-latitude regions is most dominant and exhibits unique variability with maximum ionization and TEC concentration [10]. Also, different lower atmospheric phenomena like thunderstorms, cyclones, and seismic activity like earthquakes and tsunamis, etc., are prevalent in this region, which sensibly disturbed the ionosphere [11-15], which significantly impacted radio and GPS communication. Towards upward, the total ionosphere is stratified in three or four sublayers. The D-layer (50–90 km) is mostly present during the daytime; it weakly reflects radio waves and mainly causes absorption of HF signals¹⁰, and dissipation of upward propagating waves helps deposit the energy it carried [16]. Above D, the E-layer (90–150 km) reflects some of the radio waves, shows sporadic E phenomena (Es) in summer, and during geomagnetic disturbances [17-20]. After that, the F-layer (150-500+ km) is the most significant layer for radio wave propagation and satellite-based communication systems. Several previous studies have reported that Ne concentration throughout the ionosphere exhibits variability in different temporal scales, like diurnal, seasonal, annual, semi-annual, solar cycle, etc., depending upon different spatial locations, both in latitudinal and longitudinal directions [10, 20-29]. But most of these studies focus on equatorial or polar regions; there are no single studies dedicated to ionospheric behaviour specifically over desert regions, where unique lower atmospheric phenomena, like intense solar heating linked to dust storms in the desert and thermosphere wind, etc., prevail throughout the year. Understanding the ionosphere over this region is important to improve the accuracy in radio communication and GPS signalling. At the same time, this type of study has a sensitive impact on successfully implementing the regional regular/irregular variability to the global ionospheric model and space weather forecasting.

Table1. Seasonal lower atmospheric characteristics in the great Thar desert

Months	Season	Characteristics
March–June	Summer	Extreme heat (>45°C), Loo winds, dust storms
July–September	Monsoon	Scanty rain, localized flooding
October–November	Post-Monsoon	Mild temperatures, dry weather
December–February	Winter	Cold nights (near 0°C), fog in some areas

Beside this, now a days human beings are using this region heavily for multiple purpose and establishing lots of communication systems here. So, background knowledge about the Ionosphere in different temporal scale could be crucial to operate all these technologies and fulfil the purpose. As this region is under the low to mid-latitude, study about ionosphere particularly for this region in long term scale is significant and lack of sufficient number of in-situ continuous measurement network and lack availability of long-term study is a big issue. In this respect, the Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellite is an alternative to overcome this data sparsity and in this study COSMIC-RO LEO satellite data have been used for five-year time period starting 2020 to 2024 which include Low to Moderate and High Solar Activity phases of 25th solar cycle

Section 2 describes data and method of analysis. Result and Discussion are mentioned in section 3, and summary is given in section 4.

Materials and Methods:

Data Acquisition and Quality Control

Data acquisition is crucial for observational studies; in this case, COSMIC satellite level 2 vertical profile data (“ionPrf”) for 2020 to 2024 was obtained from the COSMIC website (<http://www.cosmic.ucar.edu>), along with solar 10.7 cm flux and geomagnetic storm index data for the same period retrieved from the World Data Centre (<http://www.ukssdc.ac.uk>) of UKSSDC, UK and from the websites (<http://wdc.kugi.kyoto-u.ac.jp>) of Kyoto, Japan respectively.

COSMIC satellites require nearly 100 minutes to orbit the Earth, making it difficult to obtain real-time ionospheric data for a specific location; thus, a $10^\circ \times 10^\circ$ boxcar region was established to gather those vertical electron density profiles, which were filtered out based on geographic area bounded by 20°N - 30°N latitude and 70°E - 80°E longitude and specific conditions ($F10.7 \leq 250$ sfu and $\sum Kp \leq 30$), while excluding unreadable or incomplete profiles. All the available data are in NETCDF format. Besides the peak parameters (NmF2 and HmF2) other two parameters, BIEC (IEC is equivalent to TEC and $1\text{TECU}=1\text{E}+16$ el/m²) and TIEC were calculated using the equations: (1)

$$(BIEC, TIEC) = \int_{(Balt, HmF2)}^{(HmF2, Talt)} Ne(z) dz \quad (1)$$

In the above equation (Eq. 1), Balt and Talt are the Mean Sea Level Altitude (MSL_Alt) at the bottom and top point of the bottom and topside Ionosphere respectively.

$$ECR = TIEC / BIEC \quad (2)$$

To curtail the effect of diurnal variability in the ionospheric signature to be detected, if any, we finally calculate the daily weighted mean of each parameter using equation (2). Each day (i.e., 24 hours) is being divided into four equal-length (six hours) LT sub-intervals: $0 \leq LT < 6$, $6 \leq LT < 12$, $12 \leq LT < 18$, and $18 \leq LT < 24$, and thereafter, all the parameters (here P) associated with these four sub-intervals have been assigned the weights 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively with number of profiles N_4 , N_3 , N_2 , N_1 .

$$P(\text{ave}) = \frac{(4N_4P + 3N_3P + 2N_2P + N_1P)}{(4N_4 + 3N_3 + 2N_2 + N_1)} \quad (3)$$

Result and Discussion:

Solar F10.7 and $\sum Kp$ Index Variations

Fig. 1 illustrates the solar flux at 10.7 cm and the geomagnetic index $\sum Kp$ from 2020 to 2024, highlighting the rising phase of solar cycle 25, which started in December 2019 and reached its peak around October 2024. In the initial two years 2020 and 2021 the flux values lie within 75-85 sfu exhibiting calm conditions and thereafter in 2022-2024 these values reached up to 320 sfu. Almost 98% of the days during this period solar flux remains below 250 sfu (see Fig. 1a), interspersed with few instances of unusual variation particularly in November 2020, December 2023 and during High Solar Activity (HSA) days in late 2024.

Figure 1 -- (a)The day-to-day solar flux at F10.7 cm for 2020 - 2024; and (b) $\sum Kp$ index for 2020 – 2024.

Throughout the 1827-day observation period, $\sum Kp$ values consistently remained below 30 (see Fig. 1b) for nearly 98-99% of the time, with only a few irregular spikes coinciding with significant solar flux fluctuations (in November 2020, January-February 2023, and August-October 2024), underscoring the sun's impact on Earth's magnetic field, as established by previous studies linking solar [20, 21, 23, 30] and geomagnetic [31-35] activity to ionospheric variability over different geographic location.

Variation in NmF2 and HmF2

Peak parameter values, or NmF2 and HmF2, are plotted for the five-year period 2020–2024 in Fig. 2. The concentration of HmF2 is shown in the right panel, while that of NmF2 is shown in the left. The 7-day running mean is represented by the red lines in each plot, which lessens the extreme volatility and makes it easier to identify underlying trends and notice notable changes in the data.

Figure. 2-- The day-to-day weighted averaged values of NmF2 and HmF2 are plotted for the period of 2020 – 2024, The red line represents 7-days running mean and the gap is due to nonavailability of the data.

It is evident from the left panel that the concentration of NmF2 varies semi-annually; the annual twin-peak concentration is shown from March to May (spring) and September to November (Autumn). In contrast, it displays annual twin-dip values from December to February (winter) and June to August (summer). On the other hand, the height of peak electron concentration (i.e., HmF2) exhibits annual variability with an annual peak during May-July (pre-monsoon) and an annual dip near December-January (winter season). In yearly variation, from 2020 to 2021 the level of HmF2 is more or less flat with values ranging in 220 - 330 km except two or three days. However, in 2022, 2023, and 2024, this level of yearly dips and peaks significantly shifted upward, with values 236–368 km, 262–392 km, and 265–440 km, respectively. In this low to mid-latitude region, the amount of solar ionization is high particularly during the autumn and spring seasons in the bottom side F layer of the ionosphere. In addition to the peak level of solar energy deposition [23, 24, 30, 33, 35], particularly during HSA, there might be other

sources of influences in this area, such as $E \times B$ vertical drift [36], chemistry, meridional neutral winds, and the ratio between [O] and [N2] [25, 29] which pulls down the height of peak electron concentration (HmF2) into the F1 region in the range 220-265 km [25, 28, 30, 33, 36].

Variation in IEC

Variations in IECs over the five-year period from 2020 to 2024 were plotted in figure 3. The panels on the right display TIEC values, while the panels on the left display BIEC values. The purpose of the red lines in each plot, which represent the 7-day running mean, is to lessen the extreme volatility so that major changes in direction and underlying trends in the data can be easily identified. Over this region, it is evident that both IECs exhibit semi-annual variation that is nearly identical to NmF2 exhibiting twin-peaks in the spring (March to May) and Autumn (September to November); in contrast, they exhibit the annual twin-dip in the winter (December to February) and summer (June to August) [27, 37]. With the exception of a few irregular variations, the level of IECs in 2020 and 2021 is essentially flat (see Figs. 3a, 3b, 3f, and 3g). But from the next years, however, both the annual dips and peaks are markedly elevated. This result also largely agreed with the results of the study by Mondal et al. [22] over Kolkata covering the raising phase of 24th solar cycle. The annual peaks in IEC during these months throughout the observation period are attributed to or caused by the sum of the Ne concentrations. The increase in solar activity from 2020 to 2024 plays a crucial role in the fluctuations of IEC concentration, with the Equatorial Ionization Anomaly (EIA) being a significant factor in this region [22], especially during the HSA [25, 29, 30]. Here the question arises: which region of the ionosphere over the thar desert experiences faster solar ionization? In the next para it will be addressed in details.

Figure. 3 -- The day-to-day weighted averaged values of BIEC and TIEC are plotted for the period of 2020 – 2024, The red line represents 7-days running mean and the gap is due to nonavailability of the data.

Electron Content Ratio (ECR) Variation

Figure. 4 provides the most sensitive information about the comparative behaviour of Ne concentrations in the top and bottom side ionosphere. Though it is evident from Fig. 3 that both the IECs have a higher level of correlation (of $r = 0.7+$) between each other for the whole observation period and the correlation of solar flux (i.e. F10.7) with NmF2, HmF2, IECs and ETEC are 0.69, 0.56, 0.74, 0.70 and 0.09 respectively, meaning that the concentration of Ne and its height are significantly controlled by the sun throughout the vertical extent of the ionosphere except E layer. On the other hand, the correlation of geomagnetic index with all these parameters are near about 0.25+ except for the E-layer electron content (ETEC), which attributes a comparatively low level of influence to ionosphere Ne concentration. On the other hand the typical fluctuations of ECR in Fig. 4 throughout the observation period, exhibiting annual variation with a yearly-peak during November–December and dip during June–July in which almost 91% cases it remains in between 1 to 2 and a small percentage of the cases (ECR is less than 1 in 3.41% cases and greater than 2 in 5.26% cases) either on the day of solar disturbances or on any other external forcing, such as geomagnetic disturbance, these values surpass this range. In 2020 and 2021 during LSA, ECR mostly remains above 1.5 and thereafter it slowly and gradually slides close to 1, maintaining its inherent annual variability as solar activity gradually increasing which indicate that bottom side electron content (i.e. BIEC) achieves higher values compared to topside. Therefore, it is clear that as solar flux increases gradually and reaches its peak during the HSA period, the bottom-side ionosphere ionizes more quickly than the topside.

◆ Figure 4

Figure. 4 --The day-to-day weighted averaged values of ECR are plotted for the period of 2020 – 2024, The red line represents 7-days running mean and the gap is due to nonavailability of the data.

Variation in E Layer

The daily fluctuations of the E layer's peak electron concentration (NmE) and electron content (EIEC) during the five-year period from 2020 to 2024 are shown in Fig. 5(a-j). The figure clearly indicates that both NmE and ETEC concentrations in the E region remain consistently flat in the time period April to September with comparatively low-level of concentration for all solar activity. In the rest of the months, these two parameters exhibited significant fluctuations with clear periodicity ranging from 25 to 35 days throughout the observation period, though fluctuations in ETEC is minimal, which is probably related to the 27-day solar rotation (Sripati 2012). As it is already mentioned above that both NmE and ETEC have extremely low levels of correlation 0.09 and -0.02 with solar flux F10.7 and Geomagnetic index compared to F-layer parameters. Though solar activity is the main factor for Ne concentration in the whole Ionosphere, E-layer electron concentration might be constraints to other geophysical factors, like vertical motions of gravity waves, magnetic-field effects, meteoric mass influx into the Earth's atmosphere, and the chemical processes of metallic ions, as they may also play an important role in the spatial and seasonal variations in Ne concentration¹⁹. This pattern is mostly noticeable during 2023–2024. It may be due to the relatively high solar influence that reaches deep into the E layer during these months in HAS [18, 19] Gaspirini et al. [31] reported in their study that in the low latitudes ($< 30^\circ$), the geometry of the geomagnetic field line is a crucial factor in the ionosphere-thermosphere coupling and is driven by waves originating in the tropical troposphere. Furthermore, a sharp increase in the daily NmE concentration has been noted in May, June, and July 2020–2022, as well as in a few cases in 2023 and 2024. According to Ranjan et al, [38] and Yu et al, [19], these particular cases of abrupt increases in the upper limits of NmE may be caused by abrupt increases in the Ne concentration in the sporadic Es layer, which have strong seasonal and spatial variability. Furthermore, EIEC has been observed to fluctuate periodically between 23 and 35 days. Crucially, from 2020 to 2024, electron concentration and content (i.e., NmF2, IECs) in the F layer exhibit notable higher-high concentration with increasing solar flux, whereas those in the E layer have stayed continuously flat, suggesting that solar activity has a relatively low impact on the E layer in comparison to the layer above.

Figure. 5 -- The day-to-day weighted averaged values of NmE and EIEC are plotted for the period of 2020 – 2024. The right panels are for EIEC, and the left panels are for NmE. The red line represents 7-days running mean and the gap is due to nonavailability of the data.

Conclusion:

Here, COSMIC satellite data over a 10° box size region have been analysed to investigate the long-term variation trend in the ionosphere over the great thar desert. This is the first time that LEO satellite data has been used to study the variation of various ionospheric parameters over this region. In F layer NmF2 and IECs exhibit semi-annual variation, whereas, HmF2 displaying annual variation. In seasonal variation NmF2 and IECs shows roughly the same pattern of variability with yearly twin-peaks in the Autumn and spring and yearly twin-dips in the winter and summer respectively. In case of E layer, NmE and EIEC are consistently flat in both LSA and HAS, while the F layer's parameters are highly proportionate to solar activity suggesting that solar activity has a relatively low impact on the E layer in comparison to the layer above. In addition to solar activity, E-layer Ne concentration might be constraints to other

geophysical factors, like vertical motions of gravity waves, magnetic-field effects, meteoric mass influx into the Earth's atmosphere, and the chemical processes of metallic ions, as they may also play an important role in the spatial and seasonal variations in Ne concentration. From the ECR analysis it is evident that though during LSA Ne concentration in both the bottom and topside F layer almost similar, as solar flux start increasing the bottom-side F layer ionizes more quickly than the topside.

Acknowledgements

COSMIC satellite data were downloaded from website <http://www.cosmic.ucar.edu>. Author would like to thanks WDC Geomagnetic Data Centre, Kyoto University, Japan for providing geomagnetic indices and UKSSDC, UK for providing F10.7 cm solar flux data.

Conflict of interest

The author declare that he has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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